

Mobilization of Phosphate in Relation to Ferrous-Ferric Equilibrium in Soil

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The mobilization of native and applied phosphate in relation to ferrous-ferric equilibrium in soil has been studied. Native phosphate has no significant and immediate role on the conversion of ferrous iron to ferric state. But the increase in phosphate activity enhances the degree and rate of oxidation of ferrous ions and as a result most of the applied phosphate are transported to the non-labile pool. The fixation of applied phosphate particularly in acid soils is very little effected by the exchangeable ferric iron. Possibly it is the free ferric oxide which is active in retention of phosphate.

WHEN a soluble phosphatic material is added to soil, it reacts with different components of soil and becomes relatively unavailable to plants. Among the various components, iron and aluminium and their free oxides are most important¹⁻⁶. Dhar and Saxena⁷ reported that the applied phosphate yielded highest amount of Fe-P in acid and neutral soils and Ca-P in alkaline soils; but Al-P did not follow this trend. Wild⁸ noted the reduction in phosphate fixation caused by the removal of iron and aluminium oxides from soil colloids and the increase in phosphate fixation caused by addition of iron and aluminium compounds.

The present investigation has been carried out with a view to study the reversion of ferric iron to ferrous iron and vice-versa and its relation to available phosphate in soils.

Experimental

Seven different soil samples of West Bengal were used for the present investigation. Two acid terai soils from Alipurduar and Phansidewa belonging to

the northern district, two lateritic soils and one red soil from Bankura, Jhargram (Midnapore) and Purulia respectively, one typical alluvial soil from Chakdah (Nadia) and one coastal alluvium from Kakdwip (24-Parganas) were obtained as usual (0-20 cm), air dried under shade, ground and sieved through a 0.2 mm sieve. The relevant characteristics of the soils are given in table 1.

50 g portions of each soil were taken in plastic containers and subjected to the following treatments. In one set phosphorus was added to the soil in the form of KH_2PO_4 at the rate of 100 ppm of P and in a second set ferrous iron in the form of freshly prepared FeSO_4 solution was added at the rate of 50 ppm of Fe while a third set contained both P and Fe^{2+} at the rates same as mentioned above. One set of soil samples was kept untreated which served as control. Distilled water was added to the samples in quantities corresponding to 50 per cent of the water holding capacity of the respective soils and the samples were incubated at room temperature for a maximum period of 6 weeks. Loss of moisture during incubation, as determined by difference in

TABLE 1—PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS

Soils	pH (1 : 2)	Organic Carbon (%)	Clay Content (%)	C.E.C. (me/100 g)	Water holding capacity (%)	Free Fe_2O_3 (%)	Available phosphorus (ppm)	Total phosphorus (ppm)	Dominant clay minerals
Alipurduar	5.4	1.060	28.0	8.9	50	0.87	14.8	500	Illite
Phansidewa	4.9	1.055	28.0	8.9	54	1.03	8.0	452	Illite
Bankura	5.6	0.600	20.0	10.2	35	1.82	3.2	276	Kaolinite
Jhargram	5.1	0.435	30.0	7.5	52	2.46	9.0	252	Kaolinite
Purulia	6.8	0.351	16.8	13.2	30	1.50	7.2	268	Kaolinite
Kakdwip	6.0	0.825	70.0	29.2	62	1.86	19.0	515	Illite
Chakdha	6.6	0.800	26.0	31.7	60	1.90	6.5	140	Illite

weights, was made up every day by adding requisite quantity of distilled water.

About 15 g of soil were drawn out with the help of a spoon-headed spatula at intervals of 7, 21 and 42 days, weighed and subjected to the determination of available phosphate and exchangeable ferrous and ferric iron respectively.

Available phosphate of the soil samples were extracted by Olsen's method and the phosphate content was determined by the colorimetric procedure as described by Jackson⁹.

Exchangeable ferrous and ferric iron were determined colorimetrically by *o*-phenanthroline reagent as developed by Saywell¹⁰ using normal ammonium acetate solution at pH 7.0 and pH 3.0 respectively as extractants.

A Spectronic-20 (Bausch and Lomb) spectrophotometer was used for all colorimetric measurements. The wavelengths of light beam employed were 608 nm and 490 nm for the determination of phosphorus and iron respectively.

All the reagents and chemicals used in the present investigation were of A.R. quality.

Results and Discussion

The results of available phosphate determination are given in table 2. It appears from the data that while the original or untreated soils indicated a gradual increase in available phosphate status on

as due to ion exchange on the Kaolinite type of clay minerals.

The increase in available P status of the original soils on incubation may be ascribed to the gradual conversion of species like FePO_4 and AlPO_4 to the corresponding hydroxy or basic phosphates due to slight increase in soil pH by the influence of moisture. The rate of increase in fixation of applied phosphate indicates the kinetic of phosphate precipitation or phosphate exchange reaction by the appropriate constituents of the corresponding soils. Although the highly acidic Phansidewa soil exhibits an initial low degree of fixation, the subsequent increase in fixation on incubation was found to be maximum in this soil. The limited moisture status of the soil probably delayed the attainment of equilibrium point of phosphate fixation reactions involving active iron and aluminium present in it.

All the Fe^{2+} treated soils recorded a gradual decrease in available—P status on incubation. The Phansidewa soil showed a minimum while the lateritic Jhargram soil indicated maximum decrease in available phosphate. High acidity and high organic matter content of the former soil must have prevented the added ferrous iron from being oxidised and consequently precipitation of insoluble FePO_4 has been reduced. The low organic matter content, relatively higher Kaolinite dominant clay percentage and high free ferric oxide content may be responsible for quicker oxidation of Fe^{2+} ions followed by chemical precipitation of soluble-P already present in latter soil. Possibly, the Fe^{2+} ions might have

TABLE 2—AVAILABLE PHOSPHATE (PFM) IN THREE DIFFERENT INCUBATION PERIODS (on oven dry basis)

Soils	7 days				21 days				42 days			
	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe^{++} -treated	P+ Fe^{++} -treated	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe^{++} -treated	P+ Fe^{++} -treated	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe^{++} -treated	P+ Fe^{++} -treated
Alipurduar	15.40	24.25	13.70	18.00	16.00	21.10	12.60	16.80	16.40	19.30	10.20	14.20
Phansidewa	8.85	29.80	8.00	15.40	9.70	21.10	7.00	12.60	9.80	17.20	6.65	10.80
Bankura	4.00	13.40	3.45	8.00	4.60	10.30	3.00	6.30	4.75	8.40	3.00	4.70
Jhargram	9.10	21.60	2.75	18.00	9.20	18.30	trace	11.90	9.40	16.20	trace	8.20
Purulia	7.75	21.15	6.95	13.10	8.00	17.70	8.00	10.90	8.20	14.50	5.10	8.40
Kakdwip	20.00	27.00	18.10	20.25	20.60	24.00	17.10	18.30	20.50	21.80	14.30	16.20
Chakdah	7.10	15.60	6.80	8.90	8.40	11.40	6.90	7.40	8.25	9.00	4.20	5.80

prolonging the period of incubation the phosphate treated soils exhibited a rather decreasing trend. It is obvious that under the restricted soil moisture condition nearly 90 per cent of the applied soluble phosphate undergo fixation within 7 days of incubation. The minimum phosphate fixation (~80%) was observed in highly acidic Phansidewa soil and lateritic Jhargram soil. The fixation of phosphate in the soils under present study may be due to chemical precipitation mainly by ferric and aluminium ions or their free hydrous oxide micelle as well

also activated the reaction sites on free ferric oxide surfaces. Relatively higher phosphate activity as indicated by the initial high available-P status of this soil may also shift the equilibrium point of the following reaction towards right :

The combined effect of phosphate and ferrous iron treatment is definitely less advantageous as is evident from the lower values of available-P for all

the soils in comparison to the values obtained for samples treated with phosphate alone. The available-P status of soils in such cases decreased steadily with duration of the incubation period. It is obvious that the increase in phosphate activity enhances the degree and rate of oxidation of Fe^{2+} ions and transport most of the applied phosphate to the non-labile pool.

The results of ferrous iron determination as shown in table 3 indicate marginally increasing trend for exchangeable Fe^{2+} status in all soils with the period of incubation. On phosphate treatment, an immediate lowering of exchangeable Fe^{2+} content was observed in all cases. No further significant change was observed on extending the period of incubation. Only the Phansidewa soil recorded an increase in exchangeable Fe^{2+} status. Obviously, the higher acidity of this soil encourages the Fe^{2+} ions to remain in solution. Since this soil initially contained a very small amount of Fe^{2+} , the immediate effect of increasing phosphate activity was to depress the Fe^{2+} activity almost to zero level due to decrease in formal potential of the Fe^{II} - Fe^{III} system.

incubation. Nearly 7-8% of added iron are transformed to the ferric state or immobilised in 7 days. Subsequent conversion was found to take place at a much slower rate obviously due to the fact that in presence of moisture soil samples were depleted of its oxygen content.

From table 4 it is evident that available ferric iron content of all the soils had undergone an initial reduction in amount. After 21 days of incubation there was virtually no further change in available Fe^{3+} . The phosphate treated soils behaved more or less in a similar manner. Added phosphate could only fix 6-10 per cent of the available Fe^{3+} . With increased period of incubation under the experimental condition, i.e., at moisture level corresponding to 50% of the water holding capacity of the soils concerned, phosphate ions appeared to be rather ineffective towards Fe^{3+} immobilisation. From the results it is clear that the fixation of applied phosphate in acid soils is very little effected by the exchangeable or available ferric iron. Possibly, it is the free ferric oxide or colloidal fraction which is more active in retention of phosphate through adsorption,

TABLE 3—FERROUS IRON (PPM) IN THREE INCUBATION PERIOD
(on oven dry basis)

Soils	7 days				21 days				42 days			
	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe^{++} -treated	P+ Fe^{++} -treated	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe^{++} -treated	P+ Fe^{++} -treated	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe^{++} -treated	P+ Fe^{++} -treated
Alipurduar	9.0	7.2	15.6	11.2	9.6	7.0	16.2	10.2	10.4	7.0	18.4	9.8
Phansidewa	3.6	trace	11.8	7.2	4.7	2.0	13.4	5.8	5.3	5.0	16.0	5.2
Bankura	10.4	8.8	17.2	13.0	11.7	8.7	18.5	11.8	12.4	8.4	20.0	11.2
Jhargram	14.2	10.6	21.5	17.0	16.4	10.2	23.0	15.0	17.8	10.4	25.6	14.1
Purulia	11.2	9.0	19.3	13.8	12.5	9.0	20.4	14.0	13.8	8.9	22.8	12.8
Kakdwip	15.3	13.0	23.6	19.0	17.0	12.6	26.0	16.3	18.2	12.4	29.0	16.0
Chakdah	13.4	11.0	20.5	17.0	14.4	11.0	22.2	16.2	16.2	10.8	25.0	15.4

The effect of application of $FeSO_4$ to the soil was, in general, an increase in Fe^{2+} activity. But, while 50 ppm of soluble iron was added to each soil, after 7 days of incubation only an increase of about 8 ppm over control was observed. It is interesting to note that in respect of ferrous iron removal all the soils behave in a similar manner irrespective of their available-P status. It seems that native phosphate has no significant and immediate role on the conversion of ferrous iron to the ferric state. Restricted moisture level may be partly responsible for this. On extending the period of incubation, however, the influence of organic matter, clay percentage and their nature could be important. Decreased Fe^{2+} activity was noticed after 42 days of incubation in the soils which were richer in organic matter content.

On applying phosphate along with 50 ppm iron as Fe^{2+} in each soil, available ferrous ion status was found to decrease steadily with increasing period of

occlusion or chemical precipitation as hydroxy phosphates.

Out of 50 ppm Fe^{2+} added, about 30 ppm had undergone rapid oxidation to increase the available Fe^{3+} status of all the soils. On extending the incubation period a tendency for decreasing available ferric iron was observed which might be due to fixation or by precipitation, hydrolysis or retention by clay-organic matter complex. The tendency was most pronounced for the Kakdwip soil which contained as high as 70% clay and 0.825% organic carbon and also for the organic matter rich acid soil of Phansidewa which support the view that considerable amount of iron may be retained through the latter mechanism.

The addition of phosphate along with Fe^{2+} had an immediate depressing effect on total available ferric iron. On further incubation the reaction proceeded at a much slower but still considerable rate. Phosphate ions depress the redox potential

TABLE 4—EXCHANGEABLE FERRIC IRON (PFM) IN THREE INCUBATION PERIODS (on oven dry basis)

Soils	7 days				21 days				42 days			
	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	P+Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	P+Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	P+Fe ⁺⁺ -treated
Alipurduar	76.0	70.0	106.0	96.0	74.0	67.0	104.0	92.0	74.0	67.0	104.0	92.0
Phansidewa	64.0	60.0	98.0	90.0	61.0	60.0	96.0	88.0	61.0	60.0	93.0	86.0
Bankura	300.0	288.0	328.0	306.0	295.0	284.0	323.0	296.0	295.0	284.0	320.0	298.0
Jhargram	200.0	189.0	230.0	212.0	195.0	185.0	224.0	204.0	195.0	186.0	222.0	203.0
Purulia	80.0	72.0	112.0	98.0	78.0	69.0	110.0	94.0	77.0	68.0	106.0	92.0
Kakdwip	40.0	36.0	70.0	64.0	37.0	35.0	68.0	60.0	37.0	35.0	66.0	60.0
Chakdah	160.0	152.0	190.0	178.0	157.0	153.0	184.0	174.0	156.0	152.0	184.0	170.0

TABLE 5—F_p³⁺/F_p²⁺ RATIOS IN THREE INCUBATION PERIODS

Soils	7 days				21 days				42 days			
	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	P+Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	P+Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	Un-treated	P-treated	Fe ⁺⁺ -treated	P+Fe ⁺⁺ -treated
Alipurduar	8.4	9.7	6.8	8.5	7.7	9.6	6.4	9.0	7.1	9.6	5.5	9.4
Phansidewa	17.7	60.0	8.3	12.5	13.0	30.0	7.2	15.2	11.5	12.0	5.8	16.5
Bankura	28.8	32.7	10.07	23.5	25.3	32.6	17.4	25.1	23.8	33.8	16.0	26.6
Jhargram	14.1	17.8	19.7	12.5	11.9	17.1	9.7	13.6	10.9	17.9	8.7	14.4
Purulia	7.1	8.0	5.8	7.1	6.2	7.7	5.4	6.7	5.6	7.6	4.6	7.2
Kakdwip	2.6	2.8	2.96	3.4	2.2	2.8	2.6	3.7	2.0	2.8	2.3	3.7
Chakdah	11.9	13.8	9.3	10.5	10.9	13.9	8.3	10.7	9.6	14.07	7.3	11.0

of Fe²⁺-Fe³⁺ system and enhance the rate of oxidation of Fe²⁺ which are subsequently precipitated as simple or basic ferric phosphates.

Changes of ferric to ferrous ratio, [Fe³⁺]/[Fe²⁺] as evident from their available status are shown in table 5. It is found from the data that phosphate application has virtually no effect on the redox potential of the ferrous—ferric system as exist in the native soil. However, when fresh ferrous salt is added, applied phosphate enhances the rate of oxidation of the ferrous iron by affecting the redox potential of the system concerned.

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